

Nootropic Potential of Endophytic Fungus From *Evolvulus Alsinoides* Linn. (Shankhpushpi): Bridging Traditional Wisdom with Hippocampal Histopathology and Oxidative Stress Insights

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ABSTRACT

Endophytic fungi, which reside symbiotically within plant tissues, are recognized as valuable sources of bioactive compounds often reflecting the pharmacological attributes of their host plants. *Evolvulus alsinoides* Linn., an Ayurvedic Medhya Rasayana, is traditionally acclaimed for its memory-enhancing effects. This study aimed to isolate endophytic fungi from the aerial parts of *E. alsinoides*, and evaluate their *in vivo* nootropic potential along with associated antioxidant and neuroprotective effects in an aging-induced cognitive impairment model in mice. Ethyl acetate and n-butanol fractions were prepared from the isolated endophytic fungus and administered orally at 100 and 200 mg/kg body weight. Cognitive performance was assessed using the Elevated Plus Maze and Step-Through Latency models. Brain homogenates were analyzed for oxidative stress markers like superoxide dismutase, catalase, and reduced glutathione. Histopathological examination of hippocampal sections was conducted to evaluate neuroprotective effects. Treatment with both fungal fractions resulted in significant enhancement of cognitive performance, evidenced by reduced Transfer Latency and increased Step Through Latency. Antioxidant enzyme levels were significantly restored, indicating attenuation of oxidative stress. Histological observations confirmed the preservation of hippocampal neuronal architecture. These results suggest that the both ethyl acetate and n-butanol fractions of the endophytic fungus isolated from *E. alsinoides* possess potent nootropic and antioxidant properties, and may serve as promising natural neuroprotective agents for the management of age-related cognitive decline and Alzheimer's disease.

Keywords: Acetylcholinesterase, *Aspergillus flavus*, antioxidant enzymes, Nootropic, Alzheimer's disease

INTRODUCTION

Endophytic microorganisms are symbiotic microbes that reside within plant tissues without causing visible harm to their host¹. These microorganisms represent an untapped source of bioactive compounds with potential applications in neurodegenerative disease management. Alzheimer's disease (AD) is a progressive neurodegenerative disorder characterized by cognitive decline and behavioural disturbances, underpinned by hallmark pathologies such as amyloid-beta (A β) plaques and neurofibrillary tangles^{2,3}. Despite advances in biomarker detection and therapeutic development including cholinesterase

inhibitors, NMDA receptor antagonists, and immunotherapies. Current treatments offer limited disease modification and are often hindered by adverse effects and poor adherence^{4,5}. This underscores the urgent need for novel, sustainable therapeutic strategies.

Evolvulus alsinoides Linn., an important herb in traditional Indian medicine, is valued for its cognitive-enhancing and neuroprotective properties. Its phytochemicals, including flavonoids, alkaloids, and terpenoids, have demonstrated antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and neuroprotective effects^{6,7}. Extracts of *E. alsinoides* have been shown to alleviate

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

scopolamine-induced memory deficits through acetylcholinesterase inhibition, oxidative stress reduction, and spatial memory improvement^{8,9}. Building on this knowledge, we investigated endophytic fungi from *E. alsinoides* as potential sources of neuroprotective agents. Two strains *Penicillium citrinum* NRRL 1841 (EASF-1) and *Aspergillus flavus* ATCC 16883 (EASF-2) were isolated and characterized¹⁰. Fractions from EASF-2 (EA and NB) were evaluated in aged mice using behavioural, biochemical, and histopathological endpoints to assess their nootropic potential.

This study aims to explore the neuroprotective efficacy of *E. alsinoides* endophytes against scopolamine-induced cognitive impairment, bridging traditional medicinal knowledge with experimental evidence, and testing the hypothesis that fungal-derived bioactives can improve memory and reduce oxidative stress in an AD model.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Nootropic Activity Of Endophytic Fungal Fractions From Stem Of *Evolvulus Alsinoides* Linn. (EASF-2-EA and EASF-2-NB):

Two prominent endophytic fungi namely *Penicillium citrinum* NRRL 1841 (EASF-1) and *Aspergillus flavus* ATCC 16883 were isolated from aerial parts of title plant. Ethyl acetate and n-butanol fractions of *Aspergillus flavus* ATCC 16883 (EASF-2-EA and EASF-2-NB) were selected for in-vivo nootropic activity in young and aged swiss albino mice. Institutional Animal Ethics Committee (IAEC) permission was obtained (SET/CP/IAEC/179/02 dated 25.03.2024) for animal studies, due to its significant in-vitro antioxidant, free radical scavenging and also acetylcholinesterase inhibitory potential.

Experimental Animals: Swiss mice of both sexes, categorized by age and weight, were utilized in the study to evaluate nootropic activity. The older mice, aged 28 weeks, weighed approximately 25 grams, while the younger group, aged 18 weeks, weighed around 10–12 grams. The animals were sourced from the Maratha Mandal Research Laboratory, Belgaum, and acclimatized to laboratory conditions for a period of five days prior to initiating behavioural studies.

Throughout the study, the animals were housed in an environment that provided free access to food and water and was regulated under a 12-hour light/dark cycle. Behavioural assessments were consistently conducted during the same time each day, specifically between 3:00 PM and 4:00 PM.

All experimental protocols were conducted in strict compliance with ethical guidelines outlined by the Committee for the Purpose of Control and Supervision of Experiments on Animals (CPCSEA). The study procedures were approved by the Institutional Animal Ethics Committee, ensuring that animal welfare was prioritized at every stage of the experiment.

Acute Toxicity Studies: The acute oral toxicity of the endophytic fungal fractions was assessed in accordance with the OECD Guideline 423. A total of six animals were used for the study. Three mice were administered a single oral dose of 2000 mg/kg body weight of the fungal fractions, while the remaining three animals received distilled water (10 mL/kg) as a control group to assess any potential toxic effects.

Post-administration, the animals were observed continuously for the first two hours to monitor for signs of toxicity, including convulsions, loss of righting reflex, changes in motor activity, muscle spasms, tremors, lacrimation, sedation, hypnosis, diarrhea, and salivation. Following this initial period, the mice were kept under observation for a further 14 days to identify any delayed toxic effects or mortality.

The study was conducted in adherence to the OECD guidelines, ensuring a systematic and ethical approach to toxicity evaluation¹¹.

Elevated Plus Maze (EPM) Test: The Elevated Plus Maze (EPM) test is a widely used behavioural method to evaluate short-term memory in animals. The apparatus consisted of two closed arms and two open arms, mounted on a central platform and elevated 25 cm above the ground.

The acquisition trial was conducted on the 8th day of treatment to measure transfer latency (TL), which is defined as the time (in seconds) it takes for a mouse to move completely (all four legs) from an open arm into one of the closed arms. Each mouse was placed

at the end of an open arm, facing away from the central platform, and given a maximum of 2 minutes for free exploration of the maze before being returned to its cage. On the 9th day, the retention trial was performed to assess memory retention, with a reduction in TL considered indicative of improved memory. The animals were divided into seven groups, each consisting of six mice. Group I: Young control mice (treated with normal saline), Group II: Aged control mice (treated with normal saline), Group III: Standard treatment (Piracetam 200 mg/kg, orally), Group IV: EASF2-EA-LD (aged mice, 100 mg/kg, orally), Group V: EASF2-EA-HD (aged mice, 200 mg/kg, orally), Group VI: EASF2-NB-LD (aged mice, 100 mg/kg, orally), Group VII: EASF2-NB-HD (aged mice, 200 mg/kg, orally). This structured approach allowed for a detailed assessment of the memory-enhancing potential of the test compounds ¹².

Passive Shock Avoidance (STL) Test: This fear-aggravated test is commonly used to assess learning and memory in rodents, particularly for studying central nervous system (CNS) disorders. The model relies on the animals' ability to associate an aversive stimulus (electric shock) with a specific environment, thereby learning to avoid it. The setup includes two compartments: a light compartment and a dark compartment. On the 15th day of treatment, each animal was placed in the light compartment, and the time taken to enter the dark compartment was recorded as the acquisition latency. Upon stepping into the dark compartment, the animal received a mild electric shock (0.4 mA for 2 seconds) before being returned to its home cage. On the following day (16th day), retention latency was measured by recording the time taken by the animal to move from the light compartment to the dark compartment. Longer retention latencies indicate better memory retention, while shorter latencies suggest impaired retention. This model effectively highlights the ability of test subjects to learn and recall avoidance behaviour, offering insights into potential therapeutic interventions for memory-related disorders ¹³.

Biochemical Analysis For The Estimation Of Oxidative Damage Markers In Mice Brain Homogenate: After the treatment, mice were euthanized via cervical dislocation and the brain was insulated and weighed. The collected brain was

cleaned by ice-cold saline and distinguished by 20 mg of the fleshy tissue per ml in cool phosphate buffer (pH 7.4). The homogenates remained centrifuged at 800 rpm for 5 min to distinct the nuclear debris, gained supernatant remained then used for Superoxide dismutase (SOD), Catalase (CAT) and Glutathione (GSH) activities ^{14,15}.

Superoxide Dismutase (SOD): The measurement of superoxide dismutase (SOD) activity followed the Fridovich method. This assay utilizes xanthine and xanthine oxidase to produce superoxide radicals, which interact with p-iodonitrotetrazolium violet (INT) to generate a red-coloured formazan dye. The absorbance of this dye is measured at 505 nm to determine SOD activity. The assay medium consisted of the 0.01 M phosphate buffer; CAPS (3-cyclohexylamino-1-propane sulfonic acid) buffer solution (50 mM CAPS, 0.94 mM EDTA, saturated NaOH) with pH 10.2; solution of substrate (0.05 mM xanthine, 0.025 Mm INT) and 80 U/L xanthine oxidase. SOD activity was expressed as unit per milligram protein ^{16,17}.

Catalase (CAT): Catalase (CAT) activity was assessed using the Beutler method, which measures the reduction in hydrogen peroxide concentration by monitoring absorbance at 230 nm. The reaction mixture included: 1 M Tris-HCl buffer with 5 mM disodium EDTA (pH 8.0), 1.0 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.0), 10 mM hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂). CAT activity was quantified and expressed as units per milligram of protein ¹⁸.

Reduced Glutathione (GSH): Reduced glutathione (GSH) and oxidized glutathione (GSSG) levels were determined using a commercial kit from Cayman Chemical, which employs an optimized enzymatic glutathione reductase (GR) recycling method for accurate quantification of GSH ¹⁹. 100 µL of brain homogenate was mixed with an equal volume of metaphosphoric acid, followed by centrifugation at 2000 × g for 2 minutes to precipitate proteins. To adjust the pH, 50 µL of 4 M triethanolamine was added per millilitre of homogenate. For the total GSH assay, 50 µL of the sample was combined with 150 µL of a reaction mixture containing 0.4 M 2-(N-morpholino) ethane sulfonic acid (MES), 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 6.0), 2 mM EDTA, 0.24 mM

NADPH, 0.1 mM 5,5'-dithiobis-2-nitrobenzoic acid (DTNB), and 0.1 unit of glutathione reductase (GR). The reaction proceeded at 37 °C for 25 minutes, after which total glutathione levels were determined by measuring absorbance at 412 nm, using GSSG as the standard. For GSSG measurement, GSH was eliminated from the reaction by treating the homogenate with 10 µL of 1 M 2-vinylpyridine per milliliter of sample. Reduced GSH concentration was calculated by subtracting the GSSG value from the total glutathione. All samples were analyzed in duplicate, and GSH and GSSG concentrations were expressed as µmol per gram of tissue. The GSH-to-GSSG ratio was used as an indicator of redox status, reflecting the tissue's detoxification capacity²⁰.

Histopathological Examination Of Brain Hippocampus:

Brain tissues were excised and fixed in 10% neutral buffered formal saline, followed by standard histological processing for light microscopy. Thin sections of the hippocampus were prepared and stained to assess neuronal architecture. The samples were examined under a light microscope, focusing on distinct hippocampal regions. Neuronal counts in the CA1 region were performed using a morphometric lens in a 0.25 mm² microscopic field, and the mean values were calculated. The histopathological evaluation included identifying neuronal damage such as karyorrhexis, pyknotic black neurons, and quantifying the number of dead neurons²¹.

Statistical Analysis: The results were presented as Mean ± S.E.M. Statistical analysis was conducted using one-way ANOVA, followed by Tukey's post hoc test for multiple comparisons. Data were reported as mean ± standard deviation (n = 6). IC50 values were derived from plots of percent inhibition against the logarithm of inhibitor concentration and calculated through nonlinear regression analysis using GraphPad Prism software, version 6.0.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Acute Toxicity Studies: Acute toxicity studies were carried out according to OECD guidelines 423. No mortality was observed up to 2000mg/kg body weights were for EASF-2-EA and EASF-2-NB fractions. Hence, doses of 100mg/kg and 200mg/kg body weight were selected to assess nootropic activity.

Screening Of Endophytic Fungal Fractions Of *Evolvulus Alsinoides* Linn. In Nootropic Activity Models Of Mice:

The results of the elevated plus maze test is depicted in Figure 1. Aged animals found to show increased TL as compared to normal young mice both on 8th and 9th day of the experiment. Animals treated with EASF-2-EA at high dose (200 mg/kg p.o.) and EASF-2-NB at low dose (100 mg/kg p.o.) and at high dose (200 mg/kg p.o.) showed significant decrease in TL as compared to aged control group.

Figure 1: Effect of EASF-2-EA and EASF-2-NB on Transfer Latency (TL) in the Elevated Plus Maze model

The effect of EASF-2-EA and EASF-2-NB fractions (100 mg/kg and 200 mg/kg) on cognitive performance was assessed in aged mice using the Elevated Plus Maze model. Transfer Latency (TL) time was recorded. Data are presented as Mean ± SEM (n = 6). Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey's post hoc test. ***p < 0.001, **p < 0.01 compared to the aged control group.

Passive Shock Avoidance Paradigm: STL of aged mice was significantly decreased as compared to young control mice on 16th day indicating learning and memory impairment. Animals treated with EASF-2-EA and EASF-2-NB at high dose (200mg/kg p.o.) significantly reversed the aging induced memory deficits by increasing STL of both learning and memory task as compared to aged control mice. Piracetam (200 mg/kg p.o.) showed significant increase in STL as compared with control of aged mice shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Effect of EASF-2-EA and EASF-2-NB on Step-Through Latency in the Passive Shock Avoidance (PSA) model

Cognitive retention was evaluated using the Step-Through Latency in the PSA model in aged mice treated with EASF-2-EA and EASF-2-NB. Results are expressed as Mean ± SEM (n = 6). One-way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s post hoc test was used for statistical analysis. ***p < 0.001, **p < 0.01 compared to the aged control group.

Biochemical Analysis For The Estimation Of Oxidative Damage Markers In Mice Brain Homogenate:

The effects of two fractions, EASF-2-EA (ethyl acetate fraction) and EASF-2-NB (n-butanol fraction), on SOD activity were assessed in young, aged, and treated groups. The findings highlight the potential of these fractions in modulating SOD levels, indicating their antioxidant efficacy and possible role in mitigating oxidative stress-induced damage shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Effect of EASF-2-EA and EASF-2-NB on Superoxide dismutase (SOD)

Groups	SOD (Nanomolecules/min/mg Protein)
Young control	315.8± 8.128
Aged control	162.7± 2.566
Standard	340.2± 1.312***
EASF-2-EA-LD	180.6± 0.3835
EASF-2-EA-HD	204.7± 3.551**
EASF-2-NB-LD	277.4± 1.850***
EASF-2-NB-HD	310.3± 11.30***

The data were expressed as Mean ± S.E.M (n=6) in each group. Statistical comparison were performed by one way ANOVA followed by Tukey’s post test, * Treatments like EASF-2-NB-LD (***p < 0.001) and EASF-2-EA-HD (**p < 0.01) significantly improved SOD activity, demonstrating dose-dependent antioxidant efficacy compared to the aged control.

Significant reduction in CAT activity was observed in the aged control group compared to the young control group, indicating oxidative stress shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Effect of EASF-2-EA and EASF-2-NB on Catalase (CAT)

Groups	Catalase (Nanomolecules/min/mg protein)
Young control	5.068 ± 0.2594
Aged control	2.304± 0.5599
Standard	6.166± 0.4119***
EASF-2-EA-LD	3.385± 0.09671
EASF-2-EA-HD	3.647± 0.2172
EASF-2-NB-LD	4.671± 0.2906**
EASF-2-NB-HD	5.248± 0.4353**

Values are expressed as mean ± SD (n = 3); Tukey’s test used for analysis. Aged control showed reduced catalase activity. Significant improvement was seen with standard (***p < 0.001) and EASF-2-NB (HD & LD, p < 0.01), while EASF-2-EA exhibited moderate, dose-related effects.

The Table 3. below presents the effect of EASF-2-EA and EASF-2-NB on glutathione (GSH) levels in different experimental groups. GSH, a critical antioxidant, was measured in terms of µg/mg protein, with values expressed as mean ± SEM.

Comparisons were made among young control, aged control, standard, and treatment groups receiving different doses of EASF-2-EA and EASF-2-NB. Statistical significance indicates the efficacy of the treatments in restoring or enhancing GSH levels.

Table 3: Effect of EASF-2-EA and EASF-2-NB on Glutathione (GSH)

Groups	GSH ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mg}$ protein)
Young control	155.4 \pm 0.5133
Aged control	91.57 \pm 0.5802
Standard	166.2 \pm 1.428***
EASF-2-EA-LD	98.59 \pm 1.164**
EASF-2-EA-HD	119.0 \pm 1.029***
EASF-2-NB-LD	135.3 \pm 1.199***
EASF-2-NB-HD	154.5 \pm 1.518***

Results are expressed as mean \pm SD (n = 3); Standard and EASF-2-NB-HD significantly restored GSH levels (**p < 0.001), with EASF-2-NB-LD (*p <

0.01) and EASF-2-EA-HD (p < 0.05) showing moderate effects.

Histopathological Examination Of Brain Hippocampus: To assess the neuroprotective and nootropic potential of EASF-2-EA and EASF-2-NB, histopathological analysis of the hippocampal region was performed in all experimental groups. Brain tissues were sectioned and stained with hematoxylin and eosin (H&E) to evaluate neuronal integrity, cellular morphology, and any structural alterations associated with aging or treatment. Particular attention was given to the hippocampal pyramidal layer and cortical architecture to identify signs of degeneration, neuronal loss, or restoration following treatment. Differences in neuronal density, nuclear morphology, and tissue organization were examined to correlate histological outcomes with the observed behavioral and biochemical findings shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Histopathological evaluation of cerebral cortex and hippocampus in aged mice after treatment with EASF-2-EA and EASF-2-NB

Representative photomicrographs of brain sections stained with H&E showing the histological changes across treatment groups. (a & b) Normal morphology of pyramidal neurons in the cerebral cortex and

hippocampus (red arrows); (c & d) Moderate proliferation of hippocampal neurons, edema, and moderate pyknotic cells; (e & f) Restoration of normal pyramidal neuronal morphology; (g & h) Pyramidal neurons with vesicular nuclei and moderate

cytoplasm, without signs of shrinkage or necrosis; (i & j) Normal pyramidal cells with abundant cytoplasm and vesicular nuclei; (k & l) Cerebral cortex with near-normal neurons exhibiting central large vesicular nuclei and hippocampal CA3 region with normal thickness and pyramidal layer; (m & n) High-dose EASF-2-NB treated group showing normal histology (black arrows indicate normal neurons).

CONCLUSION

This study validates the role of fungal symbionts in the traditional use of *Evolvulus alsinoides* for cognitive enhancement and highlights the potential of endophytic fungi as sources of novel nootropic agents. Future research should focus on isolating active compounds, understanding their mechanisms, and evaluating clinical applications.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors are grateful to the institution for providing necessary facilities to carry out this work. Technical assistance in plant authentication and histopathological studies is also acknowledged.

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HOW TO CITE: Vaishali Todkar*, Prasanna Habbu, Venkatrao Kulkarni, Smita Madagundi, Chetan Savant, Nootropic Potential Of Endophytic Fungus From *Evolvulus Alsinoides* Linn. (Shankhpushpi): Bridging Traditional Wisdom With Hippocampal Histopathology And Oxidative Stress Insights., *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, 1 (12), 120-127. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17779001>

